

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF LOW VELOCITY IMPACT & COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT OF SANDWICH COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Sandwich composite structures are the essential components of modern lightweight high speed boats and naval ships. Floating object impact on the sandwich composite hulls and associated damage may be critical in its fatigue life and damage tolerance. While the structure of the sandwich hulls and operating speeds are known, the size and angle of incidence of the floating body is not known a priori. Design of such structures for damage tolerance and fatigue life is important and requires rigorous experimental and computational analysis.

Present research will utilize the state-of-the-art progressive composite damage model, MAT162 [1, 2], in explicit dynamic finite element analysis code LS-DYNA and study the low velocity impact (LVI) of spherical floating objects on sandwich composite hull structures. MAT162 is capable of modeling seven different composite damage modes, e.g., matrix crack, delamination, fiber tension-shear, and fiber crush. Recently validated MAT162 material properties for plain weave (PW) S-2 glass/SC15 composites (Baseline) [3, 4] will be used to simulate the compression after impact (CAI) [5] behavior of sandwich composite structures.

2 Finite Element Analysis

2.1 Finite Element Model

A full 3D finite element (FE) model of a sandwich composite structure is developed using eight node solid elements (Fig. 1a). The in-plane dimension is chosen to be 600-mm × 600-mm while the thickness of the top & bottom face sheets (made from Baseline

composite) and the balsa core are taken as 6.35-mm & 50.8-mm, respectively. Mesh refinements are done in the central impact zone (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1. FE Model of LVI & CAI on Sandwich Composite Structures.

Fig. 1 shows the full 3D FE model and the corresponding cross-section. In order to model the compression after impact (CAI) followed by low velocity impact (LVI), two picture frames of width & thickness, 60-mm × 30-mm, are also modeled.

2.2 Boundary & Initial Conditions

2.2.1 Low Velocity Impact (LVI)

In case of LVI, the picture frames are not used and the edges of the sandwich plates are perfectly clamped. Three different spherical projectiles of diameter, $D_p = 25.4\text{-mm}$ ($m_p = 67\text{-g}$), 50.8-mm (m_p

= 537-g), and 101.6-mm ($m_p = 4303\text{-g}$), are chosen (Fig. 2). A wide range of impact velocity of the spherical projectile is used, e.g., $V_I = 25\text{ m/s} \sim 500\text{ m/s}$.

Fig. 2. FE Model & Boundary Conditions for LVI.

2.2.2 Compression After Impact (CAI)

CAI simulations are conducted only for the 50.8-mm spherical impact. In these simulations, the picture frames are used and clamped boundary conditions are used for the top surface of the top picture frame & the bottom surface of the bottom picture frame (Fig. 1a). Three impact velocities of $V_I = 0\text{-m/s}$ (Virgin), 50-m/s, & 200-m/s are considered. In-plane compressive displacement loads are applied after 2.5 ms of the projectile impact & relaxation. A total displacement of 20-mm is applied over a duration of 5.0 ms after the impact & relaxation of 2.5 ms.

2.3 Material Model & Properties

2.3.1 Material Properties for Face Sheets

The face sheets of the sandwich composite structure are modeled with the Baseline PW (24oz/yd²) S-2 glass/SC15 composites [3, 4]. Each face sheet is composed of eight glass layers stacked with $[0_2/90_2/0_2/90_2]$ architecture providing three delamination interfaces. MAT162 composite damage model is used and the material properties can be found in Ref. [3] & [4] and is also provided in Appendix A.

2.3.2 Material Properties for Balsa Core

Honeycomb material model with tabular input of material data is used for the Balsa core of density 0.266 gm/cm^3 . Fig. 3 shows the through-thickness and transverse compression behavior of the Balsa core which is used to extract the material model input. A perfectly-plastic-non-linear model is used for the through-thickness behavior and an elastic-

plastic-non-linear behavior is used for the transverse directions.

Fig. 3. Material Properties for Balsa Core.

2.3.2 Material Properties for Steel Impactor & Supports

Linear elastic material properties of steel are used. Numerical values of the density, modulus, and Poisson's ratio are taken as: 7.85 g/cm^3 , 207 GPa, & 0.29; respectively.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Low Velocity Impact

The time history of impact force for the 50.8-mm spherical projectile is presented in Fig. 4. Complete perforation of the sandwich structure is observed at higher impact velocities than the perforation limit velocity, V_{PL} , of the projectile-sandwich composite pair (Fig. 5). V_{PL} of different projectiles are determined by plotting the rebound/residual velocities as a function of the impact velocities of the projectiles (Table 1). At all impact velocities, the projectile create damages to both face sheets close to the impact site without or with complete perforation. Fig. 6 shows the delamination damage for two impact velocities, i.e., 50 m/s (impact & rebound) & 200 m/s (complete perforation) for the 50.8-mm diameter projectile (These test cases will further be considered for CAI simulations). Impact induced delamination area for three different projectiles are presented in Fig. 7 as a function of impact energy. It is evident that the delamination area increases till the perforation limit and remains constant or decreases above the perforation limit.

Fig. 4. Time History of Impact Contact Force, $D_p = 50.8\text{-mm}$, $m_p = 537\text{-g}$.

Fig. 5. Perforation Limit Velocity Profiles.

Table 1. Perforation Limit Velocity & Energy of the Sandwich Composite Structure

Projectile Mass, m_p , g (Diameter, D_p , mm)	Perforation Limit, V_{PL} , m/s (Energy, E_{PL} , kJ)
67 (25.4)	377 (4.76)
537 (50.8)	163 (7.13)
4303 (101.6)	75 (12.10)

Fig. 6. Delamination Damage, 50.8-mm (537-g) Projectile.

Fig. 6. Delamination Damage, 50.8-mm (537-g) Projectile.

3.2 Compression After Impact

Axial compressive force is presented in Fig. 7 for three different impact velocities, i.e., 0-m/s (Virgin), 50-m/s, & 200-m/s for 50.8-mm projectile. The peak axial force at failure occurred for the virgin specimen at time, $t = 4.6\text{-ms}$, value of which is found to be 1950-kN. Top view & X-sectional view of axial damage at time $t = 5.0\text{-ms}$ & at 7.0-ms are presented in Figs. 8 & 9, respectively. Note that the projectile in Fig. 9 is static (a zero impact velocity was assigned during computational simulation).

Fig. 7. Axial Compressive Force.

The peak axial compressive force at failure for the impact velocity of 50-m/s is found to be 1205-kN at time $t = 3.95\text{-ms}$. The knock-down of axial force at 50-m/s impact velocity is found to be 38% $\{(1950 - 1205) \times 100 / 1950\}$. Similarly, the peak axial force and knock-down for the impact at 200-m/s is found to be, 965-kN (at $t = 3.8\text{-ms}$) & 50%, respectively. The average residual strength (calculated in the time

range 5-ms to 7-ms) for all impact cases is found to be about 25% of the virgin axial strength of the sandwich composite structure $\{(500 \times 100 / 1950)\}$.

Fig. 8. Top View of Axial Damage for the Virgin Specimen.

Fig. 9. X-Sectional View of Axial Damage for the Virgin Specimen.

While the delamination damage at the end of the impact event for impact velocities 50-m/s & 200-m/s is presented in Fig. 6, the top view of delamination damage during CAI is presented in Figs. 10 & 11. The corresponding X-sectional views of the axial damages are presented in Figs. 12 & 13.

Fig. 10. Top View of Axial Damage for Impact Velocity, $V_I = 50$ -m/s, 50.8-mm (537-g) Projectile.

Fig. 11. Top View of Axial Damage for Impact Velocity, $V_I = 200$ -m/s, 50.8-mm (537-g) Projectile.

Fig. 12. X-Sectional View of Axial Damage for Impact Velocity, $V_I = 50$ -m/s, 50.8-mm (537-g) Projectile.

Fig. 13. X-Sectional View of Axial Damage for Impact Velocity, $V_I = 200$ -m/s, 50.8-mm (537-g) Projectile.

Even though the axial compressive failure of the impacted panels at time $t < 4.0$ -ms, the sandwich composite panels are found to progressively damage till time $t = 4.5$ -ms and showed a residual compressive strength behavior (25% of virgin strength) till the end of simulation at time $t = 7.0$ -ms.

4 Summary

Finite element analyses of LVI and CAI experiments are presented. Using a previously validated composite damage model properties and parameters for PW S-2 glass/SC15 composites, modeling and simulation of impact damage and compression after impact behavior of a sandwich composite structure is presented for different impact cases. The computational simulations provided the force, velocity, and displacement and damage maps as a function of time, from which the limit perforation velocity and damage area can be determined. In addition, for any impact scenarios, it has been shown that the axial strength of the sandwich composite structure can be predicted by simulating a numerical CAI experiment.

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Appendix A

MAT162 Material Properties & Parameters for Baseline PW S-2 Glass/SC15 Composites

Properties, Unit	PW S-2 Glass/SC15
E1, GPa	27.5
E2, GPa	27.5
E3, GPa	11.8
v21	0.11
v31	0.18
v32	0.18
G12, GPa	2.90
G23, GPa	2.14
G31, GPa	2.14
X1T, MPa	604
X1C, MPa	291
X2T, MPa	604
X2C, MPa	291
X3T, MPa	58
SFC, MPa	850
SFS, Mpa	300
S12, MPa	75
S23, MPa	58
S31, MPa	58
AM1	2.00
AM2	2.00
AM3	0.50
AM4	0.20
PHIC	10
SFFC	0.30
Crate1	0.03
Crate2	0.00
Crate3	0.03
Crate4	0.03
SOURCE	Ref. [3, 4]